

Unraveling the anchoring effect of crisis communication in cyberattack spillover crises

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ABSTRACT

A spillover crisis arises when an external organization's events create worry, ambiguity, or unfavorable perceptions for another organization. The study shows that organizational response strategies for spillover crises are influenced by an anchoring effect, where competitors' level of accommodation in their crisis response serves as an anchor point. The difference between accommodative and advocative crisis responses becomes more pronounced when the anchor response has a lower level of accommodation. Additionally, stakeholders' confidence in an organization's ability to manage crises can predict its reputation during spillover crises. If an organization chooses to respond with advocacy, it may experience a decline in reputation compared to adopting a competitor's accommodative anchor response due to decreased stakeholder confidence. Conversely, using an accommodative response can result in a higher organizational reputation than following a competitor's advocative anchor response since it boosts stakeholder confidence. The study highlights the importance of considering situational factors such as competitor responses in the contingency theory of accommodation. Additionally, this study provides evidence that a continuum of public response confidence could be another valuable tool for understanding how crises impact reputation.

1. Introduction

In 2023, a vulnerability emerged in Progress Software's MOVEit file transfer app, leading to ransomware gang cyberattacks on over 2700 organizations globally. These include government bodies, financial institutions, and various other public and private sector entities that use MOVEit in their supply chains, according to The National Cyber Security Centre (The National Cyber Security Centre, NCSC, 2023). Consequently, as reported by Emsisoft (2023), a staggering 94 million pieces of customer or employee data were stolen. Financial management research emphasizes the contagious nature of cyberattack crises, showing their capacity to impact financial behaviors and connections across various sectors. In the aftermath of a cyberattack on a firm, investments toward its suppliers and similar firms, characterized by industry and geographical proximity, also experience declines in the subsequent years (Garg, 2020). Furthermore, a study on cryptocurrency

markets notes significant spillover interdependence among the three major cryptocurrencies (Bitcoin, Litecoin, and Ethereum), indicating diminished portfolio diversification opportunities for cryptocurrency investors when one of them falls victim to a cyberattack (Caporale et al., 2021). This backdrop presents a crucial problem: the existing literature, while rich in insights into crisis response for directly affected organizations, offers limited guidance for those grappling with spillover effects. Previous studies have examined various response strategies, ranging from advocative stances (Syed, 2019; Bentley and Ma, 2020) to more accommodative approaches (Knight & Nurse, 2020; Thomas et al., 2022). However, these findings do not sufficiently address the strategic needs of organizations indirectly impacted by a crisis, particularly in scenarios where their peers have already initiated proactive responses (e.g., Office of the Australian Information Commissioner's (OAIC) guidance for data breach preparation and response, Office of the Australian Information Commissioner, 2023a). The contagious nature of

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cyberattack crises poses a challenge in providing comprehensive guidance for organizations in such situations.

A spillover crisis happens when events from an external organization create worry, doubt, or negative perceptions for another organization (Veil et al., 2016). Previous studies indicate that the reputation of a single company is closely linked to the collective reputation of its industry (Barnett, 2007; Barnett & Hoffman, 2008). This is because it can be challenging for the public to distinguish between individual performance and that of their competitors (Barnett & King, 2008). A notable example occurred in 2015 when Volkswagen's emissions scandal negatively impacted the entire German automobile industry's image (Laufer & Wang, 2018). Thus, the actions and reputations of other organizations can have a significant impact on the reputation and legitimacy of an organization in a closely related industry. This negative spillover phenomenon is also known as reputational interdependence (Veil et al., 2016). Laufer and Wang's (2018) research suggests that organizations sharing a similar country of origin, industry, organizational type, or positioning strategy as the affected organization are at higher risk of experiencing a spillover crisis. To navigate these spillover crises, Barnett and Hoffman (2008) have identified three main strategic themes: competing with others to improve one's own reputation ("keeping up with the Jones's"), collaborating with others to enhance the industry's overall reputation ("teaming up with the Jones's"), or setting oneself apart from competitors ("fencing out the Jones's"). However, our study proposes a fourth strategy theme called "anchoring off the Jones's" in response to spillover crises.

Public's perception towards organizational crisis response may experience an anchoring bias. Anchoring effect is a cognitive bias that occurs when people rely too heavily on the first piece of information they receive (the anchor) when making subsequent judgments or decisions under uncertainty. Tversky and Kahneman (1974) were among the first to explain the anchoring-and-adjustment heuristic. They proposed that people tend to make insufficient adjustments when estimating a value based on an initial anchor or parameter, resulting in biased estimates toward the anchor values. Strack and Mussweiler (1997) further elaborated on this concept by stating that anchor values act as reference points for individuals to adjust their range of plausible answers. This adjustment process involves moving towards the range of plausible answers based on an initial value, which can be effortful (Furnham & Boo, 2011).

Therefore, through a vignette experiment in this paper, we examine this nuanced aspect of crisis communication, examining how organizations can strategically navigate spillover crises by understanding and leveraging the anchoring effect in their response strategies. We propose that stakeholders may adjust their estimated plausible degree of accommodation in an organizational response based on what its competitors – "the Jones's" - have presented. Through anchoring off the Jones's, an organizational response that goes beyond the estimated boundaries by being more accommodating would be viewed favorably, while a response that advocates beyond stakeholders' expectations would be less favorable. The findings of this study enrich the existing literature on crisis communication by providing empirical evidence and theoretical insights into managing spillover crises, an area that has been underexplored in current research.

2. Literature review and hypothesis development

2.1. Crisis communication and reputation repair in cyberattack crisis

Cyberattacks, characterized by unauthorized incursions into digital systems, have escalated not only in frequency but also in their capacity to impair organizational reputation. A cyberattack is described as a deliberate attempt to unlawfully obtain, manipulate, disable, or destroy data, applications, or other assets by gaining unauthorized access to a network, computer system, or digital device (IBM., 2023). Cyberattack crisis can inflict significant harm on individuals and thus pose a

reputational threat to organizations and their information systems (Thomas et al., 2022). Instances of such harm may involve the risks of financial fraud conducted in the victim's name or individuals becoming targets for their valuables due to the disclosure of sensitive personal information. In the cybersecurity domain, some researchers define organizational reputation as the collective evaluation or perception of the organization's capacity to fulfill the expectations of the public in securing their information (Syed, 2019). This definition emphasizes the significance of response strategy in rebuilding customers' confidence in an organization's ability to manage their personal data responsibly and mitigate the potential reputational loss a cyberattack can result (Office of the Australian Information Commissioner, 2023b).

Previous studies have examined the appropriate responses for organizations that have experienced a cyberattack in order to mitigate reputation threats following a data breach. Some researchers, following a social media content analysis after the US Home Depot data breach (Syed, 2019), advocate for an advocative stance. Framing the organization as a "victim" of an attack, for instance in the context of external threats, is observed to result in less reputational damage compared to "accidental" (e.g., system vulnerabilities, human manipulation) or "intentional" frames (e.g., ethical misdemeanors, poor controls, weak governance structures). Bentley and Ma (2020) support Syed's findings that acknowledging a company's responsibility did not have an advantage on organizational reputation repair and suggest that companies should position themselves as victims unless their responsibility is evident. Conversely, others propose a more accommodative stance. Thomas et al. (2022) demonstrated the effectiveness of acknowledging the organization's responsibility in apologizing when responding to cyber crises in Australia. Similarly, some findings indicate that admitting the organization's role in the cyberattack, rather than downplaying it, is common in the UK based on interviews with 13 C-level executives (see Knight & Nurse, 2020). However, there is currently no empirical evidence for organizations experiencing spillover effects from cyberattack crises on whether to adopt a more advocative or accommodative approach in their responses to mitigate reputation threats in such situations.

2.2. Contingency theory of accommodation: accommodative vs. advocative crisis response

The contingency theory of accommodation proposes that organizations have a range of strategic options when responding to a crisis, varying along a continuum from pure advocacy of the organization's interests to complete accommodation of public/stakeholder concerns and interests (Cancel et al., 1999; Coombs, 2022). The concept of "stance" in the context of an organization's crisis response refers to the degree of accommodation perceived by the public. This perception is shaped by the extent to which the organization aligns its actions and communications with public interests during conflict situations. "Stance" essentially quantifies the organization's approach to managing a crisis, ranging from highly accommodative to less accommodative, as gauged by public perception" (Pang et al., 2020). The decision of the stance depends on predisposing organizational factors like culture and leadership style as well as situational factors including external public characteristics, urgency, and severity of threat to the public (Pang et al., 2010; Zhang et al., 2004).

While the contingency theory of accommodation puts forth the overall concept that organizational crisis response can range across a spectrum from pure advocacy to complete accommodation, it does not delineate the specifics of how to match response to a given crisis situation. On the other hand, situational crisis communication theory (SCCT) builds upon the core contingency theory premise to provide clearer prescriptive guidance tailored to developing an organizational crisis response. SCCT puts forth crisis response strategies that range along the same advocacy-accommodation continuum in a way that directly links strategies to the level of responsibility the public attributes to an

organization for a crisis (Coombs, 2021; Coombs, 2022). Denial, evading responsibility, and reducing offensiveness are considered more advocative strategies while apology, corrective action, and mortification are perceived as more accommodative strategies (Pang, 2006; Coombs, 2021; Coombs, 2022).

Organizations possess the capability to tailor their crisis communication strategy to various audience segments. This adaptability, as delineated by Pang et al. (2020), is a dynamic process that operates along a continuum. This continuum forms the crux of what is termed “factor-stance-strategy management,” a critical element in crafting effective crisis communication strategies (Jin et al., 2007). The essence of this approach lies in the comprehensive assessment and incorporation of all pertinent factors that influence an organization’s response capabilities. This assessment enables organizations to strategically select and align their response strategies with the adopted stances, ensuring that the communication resonates appropriately with the targeted audience (Pang et al., 2020; Kice & Klyueva, 2022). In essence, prior literature underscores the importance of organizational agility and strategic flexibility in crisis management, emphasizing the need for informed decision-making and active stakeholder engagement. However, a notable gap in current research pertains to the empirical exploration of how predisposing and situational factors specifically influence the trajectory of an organization’s response stance along this continuum, particularly in the context of spillover crises. A deeper understanding of these factors is important, as it can significantly enhance our comprehension of how organizations calibrate their strategy selection in response to varying crisis scenarios.

2.3. Response strategies to spillover crises

Veil et al. (2016) categorized crisis response strategies into five types based on their analysis of a spillover crisis in the peanut industry. These strategies range from advocative to accommodative stances and include denial, disassociation, ingratiation, reminding, and compensation (see Fig. 1). As per SCCT, a spillover crisis may seem like a rumor because the organizations being affected are not responsible for creating the crisis. Notably, Veil et al.’s (2016) prescribed crisis response strategies that appeared to contradict SCCT recommendations for rumor crises. The SCCT recommends that organizations select response strategies depending on the amount of responsibility the public attributes to the organization to mitigate the reputational threat to the organization in crisis (cf. Coombs & Tachkova, 2022).

Arendt et al. (2017) in their qualitative meta-analysis found that corrective action is most effective, especially when combined with strategies like reducing offensiveness or bolstering. This finding supports the need for multifaceted response strategies in spillover crises. Kim et al. (Kim et al., 2009) further point out the discrepancy between crisis communication theories and practical applications, emphasizing the importance of aligning theoretical frameworks with real-world scenarios.

Denial	Denying any involvement in the cause of the crisis and specifically naming and blaming the organization responsible for the crisis.
Disassociation	Clearly stating that the organizations have no relational business ties.
Ingratiation	Thanking stakeholders for ongoing patronage and support.
Reminding	Using bolstering statements to draw stakeholder attention to the organization’s positive attributes.
Compensation	Offering coupons and discounted rates to entice stakeholders back to the organization and industry.

Fig. 1. Response strategies to spillover crisis (Adapted from Veil & Dillingham, 2020, p366.).

The higher the crisis responsibility that stakeholders attribute to the organization in crisis, the more accommodative the strategy the organization must adopt (Coombs, 2021). However, simply denying rumors during a crisis, as recommended by SCCT, is insufficient (Veil & Dillingham, 2020). This is because spillover crises create a paradoxical situation where an organization faces not only reputational but also industry legitimacy threats despite having no responsibility for causing the crisis. Reputation is established through comparisons between organizations based on various attributes such as favorability and quality. Conversely, legitimacy is obtained when an organization adheres to socially and politically acceptable practices and gains social acceptance (Deephouse & Carter, 2005). Therefore, Veil et al. (2016) proposed that in these situations it would be more appropriate to convince the public of a substantial response to an unsubstantiated claim and suggested corrective action that combines responsibility denial with legitimacy-rebuilding strategies in response to spillover crises. Ma and Zhan (2016) emphasize the strong impact of attributed responsibility on reputation, highlighting the critical role of matching response strategies with the level of responsibility perceived by the public.

A spillover crisis could reveal industry vulnerabilities in similar organizations. For instance, the re-accommodation crisis faced by United Airlines, where a passenger was forcibly removed from one of its planes, has revealed the vulnerability of all airlines that practice overbooking (Benoit, 2018). Previous research has shown that such exposed but non-harmful vulnerabilities should be viewed as opportunities (Veil et al., 2012). Taking corrective action to address these vulnerabilities can provide an organization with actional legitimacy and competitive advantage (Veil et al., 2016). Veil and Dillingham (2020) suggested that a corrective action response should deny any involvement in the initial crisis and subsequently outlines the measures taken to prevent a recurrence of such a crisis. This approach may present the responsive organization as a better alternative to stakeholders than those who do not address their weaknesses. While there is empirical evidence supporting this strategy for other paradoxical situations like hoaxes (Veil et al., 2012), further research is needed before recommending corrective action as a response to spillover crises. In this study, we aim to investigate the effectiveness of corrective action as a response to spillover crises compared to the responses recommended by Veil et al. (2016). Additionally, we will evaluate its efficacy when a competitor’s response is used as an anchor in such situations.

2.4. Competitor’s response as situational factor: anchoring effect in crisis communication

Predisposing factors help organizations determine their stance before a crisis communication, while situational factors determine the final response during interactions with external audiences (Pang et al., 2020). Laufer and Wang (2018) identified four key predisposing factors that can estimate an organization’s risk of crisis contagion and whether they should issue a denial. These include similarities in the country of origin, industry, organizational type, and positioning strategy. However, the decision on the final response stance is based on both predisposing and situational factors. Unfortunately, there has been insufficient exploration of how these situational factors impact the response stance for spillover crises. For instance, in such a crisis, the public’s perception of an organization’s response may vary after receiving a response from a competitor organization that is also affected. In a spillover crisis, the initial response message conveyed to stakeholders from a competitor organization may serve as an anchor and influence their perception towards the focal organization and its response to the crisis. Similarly, Jong and van der Linde (2022) refer to this as the “echo effect”, they found Volkswagen’s Dieseltgate establishes a crisis history in car industry, potentially acting as an amplifying factor for competitors facing similar crises at a later stage.

The anchoring effect can occur in crisis-related decision-making. Crises are typically characterized by a lack of information, leading to

uncertainty and potential harm to stakeholders. To mitigate this stress, it is crucial that stakeholders receive as much information as possible to feel reassured (Coombs, 2021). In times of crisis, people may resort to quick heuristics due to the lack of reliable information and the need for prompt decision-making (Paulus et al., 2022). For instance, when COVID-19, as a novel virus, first struck a country, experts needed to estimate how many response resources and funds the overall crisis response network required. This was crucial to advise policymakers for better preparation, based on their experience in responding to similar influenza outbreaks or estimations from other countries. However, this situation potentially led to anchoring bias, as experts may have anchored their estimates on past experiences or external references, impacting the accuracy of their predictions. Their study (Paulus et al., 2022) involved three groups: crisis experts, government and non-profit workers, and those laypeople affected by the crisis. The results showed that all three groups estimated lower levels of resources and funds when presented with low-anchor information, while higher levels were estimated when high-anchor information was provided. According to Wegener et al. (2010), this phenomenon is known as “confirmatory search”, where information consistent with the presented anchor reinforces the anchoring effect. Judges tend to consider the anchor value as a potentially correct answer and look for similarities between their estimate and this value, leading them to focus on aspects of the target that align with their initial impression (Mussweiler & Strack, 2001a, b). Similarly, we propose in the current study that offering a higher level of accommodation response than competitors’ anchor response can improve stakeholders’ perception of an organization, while offering a lower level can have the opposite effect.

H1. : The effect of response message framing on stakeholders’ confidence in an organization’s crisis response depends on the anchor response.

H1a. : Stakeholders’ confidence in an organization’s crisis response capabilities will be negatively affected when the organization’s response is less accommodative compared to a previously established anchor response by another entity.

H1b. : Stakeholders’ confidence in an organization’s ability to manage a crisis will be positively influenced when the organization’s response is more accommodative than the anchor response.

2.5. Confidence as an indicator of the publics’ evaluation to an organization’s crisis communication

Stakeholder’s estimation of organizational stances can be understood through their confidence in organization’s ability to handle a crisis. Pang et al. (2020) proposed a new continuum to depict the public’s response or stance towards an organization during a crisis. This continuum ranges from confidence at one end to doubt at the other, capturing the dynamic movement of public reactions over time. Doubt represents lower levels or lack of confidence and is positioned opposite to confidence on this continuum. They also suggested that an interaction between an organization’s stance (accommodation-advocacy) and the public’s stance (confidence-doubt) may have a potential spiral relationship over time. According to Earle et al. (2007), while an organization can inspire confidence, it cannot be trusted by individuals due to their limited knowledge about the organization and insufficient time to establish trust. This is because trust can only be earned gradually over time and requires comprehensive knowledge of an organization’s consistent ethical actions and values (Bowen et al., 2016). In contrast, confidence refers to a positive belief in future events based on experience or evidence (Earle et al., 2007). If stakeholders have positive past experiences or information about the organization, it is more likely to increase their confidence in it during crises (Pang et al., 2020).

According to Pang et al. (2020), stakeholder confidence in an organization’s ability to handle crisis threats is linked to the resources

available to it. In a crisis communication context, threats are evaluated based on situational demands such as danger severity and uncertainty, as well as resources like knowledge, skills, time, finance, and support from the dominant coalition. The confidence in an organization’s resourcefulness during a crisis plays a crucial role in determining how stakeholders assign blame or credit, assess their coping potential and form future expectations. Previous studies have explored the relationship between confidence and crisis preparedness from an organizational perspective. For instance, Wigley and Zhang (2014) focused on public relations professionals’ confidence in using two-way symmetrical communication to manage crises. Ruan et al. (2022) investigated government crisis management can restore confidence among tourism managers during the COVID-19 pandemic by enhancing their various senses of gain. From the public’s perspective, Persson et al. (2017) found that impartiality in public administration has a negative impact on their confidence in European Union (EU) crisis management institutions. When citizens feel they are being treated unfairly or with bias by their national authorities, they tend to place greater confidence in institutions at the EU level. However, the effectiveness of using this confidence-doubt continuum to explain stakeholders’ reactions towards an organization’s accommodation-advocacy stance, and subsequently predict their behaviors such as engagement and perception of reputation, remains uncertain without empirical evidence.

As a result, stakeholder confidence tied to crisis response strategy can directly influence organizational reputation. Reputation refers to the cumulative stakeholder perceptions of an organization built over time through assessments of corporate behavior, communication, and visual identity (Chun, 2005). Reputational threat is a major risk associated with crisis situations (Coombs, 2007). Prior studies have collectively underscored the multifaceted nature of crisis communication and its profound influence on organizational reputation, such as the timing of disclosure and crisis response strategy (Claeys et al., 2010; Claeys & Cauberghe, 2012). Effective response strategies that inspire confidence by demonstrating accountability, compassion, and capability can protect reputational assets. However, poorly handled responses that raise stakeholder doubts may significantly impair an organization’s reputation (Schwarz, 2012).

Therefore, we hypothesize that the anchoring bias in organizational response message framing can be explained by stakeholders’ confidence in the organization’s ability to handle a crisis. This, in turn, predicts their perception of the organization’s reputation based on where they fall on the public’s stance continuum (see Fig. 2).

H2. : A higher level of stakeholder confidence leads to a more positive organizational reputation perception.

3. Method

3.1. Study design and stimuli

We conducted an online experiment with a 2 (response message framing: advocative stance vs. accommodative stance) × 3 (anchor response: not present vs. advocative stance vs. accommodative stance) between-subjects design in China.

The vignette used in the experiment was about a spillover crisis in the personal cloud-based storage service industry in China. In our vignette

Fig. 2. The hypothesized conceptual model.

experiment, we focus on personal cloud storages rather than corporate clouds, driven by the prevalence of personal cloud storage software like iCloud, Dropbox, and Google Drive pre-installed in the most popular smartphones available in the market. The extensive use of personal cloud storage is driven by its superior synchronization capabilities compared to previous technologies. However, this trend has also raised concerns about privacy, as private information stored on public platforms is at a higher risk of cyber-attacks. This choice reflects the fact that laypeople, who constitute the majority of participants, are more sensitive to security and privacy threats related to their personal data in the context of cyberattack breaches.

The stimulus material began with a fictitious news report (**Appendix A**) about a security issue caused by 115 Cloud storage, which experienced a breach of user information due to hackers attacking a possible vulnerability in its sharing mechanism. The personal cloud storage user data leakage incident has caused concerns among people about the security performance of cloud storage. In response to publics' concern, Tencent Micro-Cloud (**Appendix B**) and Baidu Netdisk (**Appendix C**) respectively responded to their sharing mechanisms and security performance. The response from Tencent Micro-Cloud was selected as the anchor response before Baidu Netdisk released a response. Both organizations issued separate crisis responses framed with advocative or accommodative stances. For the former stance, both organizations denied involvement and emphasized no vulnerabilities in their sharing systems; for the latter, they provided corrective actions after disassociating themselves from the incident. Baidu Netdisk and Tencent Micro-Cloud were selected in the stimulus because they were among the most well-known personal cloud-based storage service providers in China (iiMedia Research, 2022), which would help to create a stronger sense of involvement for the participants.

3.2. Measurements

Crisis response stance framing. The manipulation of response stance framing of the organization and its competitor was measured in three dimensions. First, a one-item bi-polar scale by asking the participant to what extent they believe the response is concerned with the company's or the stakeholder's interest (where 1 represents "completely the organization's interest" and 7 represents "completely the stakeholder's interest"). Second, the scale for the degree of advocacy and accommodation was adapted from Jin and Cameron (2006) and measured respectively by asking to what extent participants rate the response from the organization as "1) in the stance of the organization itself; 2) mainly for maintaining its interest of the organization; 3) mainly for the consideration of its own reputation" and "1) yield to the public's demands; 2) promise the public on future action and procedure; 3) respond the event in the stance of its stakeholders". The reliability of the two scales in the current study was satisfactory with Cronbach alpha = 0.81 and Cronbach alpha = 0.91 respectively.

Dependent variables. The dependent variable, organizational reputation, was measured with a four-item short-form measurement of corporation reputation (Ponzi et al., 2011) including the following items: "I have a good feeling about the organization; I trust the organization; I admire and respect the organization; the organization has a good overall reputation". The scale for this dimension demonstrated high reliability (Cronbach's alpha = 0.95).

Mediating variables. Confidence in organization's capacity was measured by a 3-item scale adapted from Hon and Grunig's (1999) organizational trust scale for competence and framed in a future-oriented manner: "I feel very confident about this organization's skills; I am confident this organization has the ability to handle this event; I am confident this organization would be successful at the things it tries to do in this event." The scale for this dimension also demonstrated high reliability (Cronbach's alpha = 0.91).

Control variable. Stakeholders' pre-crisis reputation perceptions of the organizations used in the stimuli were controlled in the data

analysis. This was done to account for the "halo effect" associated with favorable pre-crisis reputations. Organizations with positive pre-crisis reputations tend to experience a buffering effect that protects them from reputational loss during a crisis (Coombs & Holladay, 2006). Publics often interpret negative publicity from third parties about organizations they favor more positively, aligning their expectations with those organizations (Claeys & Cauberghe, 2015). Controlling for pre-crisis reputation perception ensures a more accurate analysis of the impact of crisis communication on stakeholders' perceptions. The pre-crisis reputation of the organization and anchor organization was measured by asking the participants to what extent do you rate the overall reputation of the following organizations. All the measurements used in the study were seven-degree scales.

3.3. Participants and procedure

A total of 420 valid participants, who were users of Baidu cloud-based storage, were recruited for financial compensation through Credamo's online panel (individuals unable to provide a Baidu cloud storage ID and those who have participated in the pretest will be automatically excluded). Credamo is a professional data platform equipped with a sample database of over 1.5 million pre-registered participants. It offers interfaces in both Chinese and English, combining features from Qualtrics and MTurk. The average age of the participants was 31.61 (range = 18–61 years, SD = 7.70, 60% female), 89% of the participants had completed higher education and all of them had used Baidu Netdisk storage service.

Participants were firstly asked to rate the pre-crisis reputation of the focal and anchor organization. Participants were randomly assigned to one of the six vignettes. Participants were later asked to read a news report and then were presented with an anchor response from a competitor organization (Tencent) in the same industry and followed by manipulation check questions for response stance framing. After that, participants were presented with a response from the focal organization (Baidu) and asked the same manipulation check questions for response stance framing. Finally, participants were requested to complete the remaining questions concerning the focal organization. At the end of the questionnaire, participants were informed that the crisis event in the experiment was fictitious and does not exist in the real world. The entire procedure took approximately five minutes.

3.4. Pre-test

A total of 120 Chinese participants, with an average age of 30.30 (range = 18–58 years, SD = 9.14%, and 57.5% female), were recruited for financial compensation through Credamo's online panel. Table 1 presents the results of the pretest. Participants perceived that accommodative responses were more likely in stakeholders' stance than advocative responses for both focal organization ($t(118) = 3.18, p = .02$) and anchor organization ($t(118) = 4.71, p < .001$). Additionally, there was no difference in stance perception between the two organizations regarding the accommodative response ($t(118) = .94, p = .35$) or advocative response ($t(118) = .21, p = .83$).

Regarding the degree of accommodation, participants perceived that accommodative responses were more likely in stakeholders' stance than advocative responses for both the focal organization ($t(118) = 4.63, p < .001$) and the anchor organization ($t(118) = 4.52, p < .001$). Furthermore, there was no difference in accommodative stance perception between the two organizations concerning accommodative response ($t(118) = .16, p = .18$) or advocative response ($t(118) = .34, p = .74$). For the degree of advocacy, participants perceived that advocative responses were more likely in organizations' stance than accommodative responses for both the focal organization ($t(118) = 3.91, p < .001$) and the anchor organization ($t(118) = 5.24, p < .001$). Moreover, there was no difference in advocative stance perception between the two organizations regarding accommodating response (t

Table 1
Result of crisis response stance manipulation checks in pre-test.

		Bi-polar stance perception		Degree of advocation		Degree of accommodation	
Organization	Stance	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
Anchor Organization	Advocative response	3.33	2.15	5.66	1.2	4.48	1.29
	Accommodative response	4.55	2.04	4.66	1.58	5.41	0.87
Organization	Advocative response	3.25	1.99	5.62	1.22	4.56	1.29
	Accommodative response	4.88	1.81	4.5	1.47	5.63	0.92

(118) = .22, $p = .83$) or advocating response($t(118) = .18, p = .86$).

Overall, the pretest demonstrated a significant difference between advocative and accommodative responses from the two organizations. However, there was no difference in stance perception between the two organizations regarding either response type. These results suggest that the manipulation of response stance framing was successful.

4. Results

4.1. Main test

4.1.1. Manipulation checks

Table 2 shows that the results were consistent with the pre-test. A significant difference was found between advocative and accommodative responses from the two organizations, while there was no difference in stance-framed responses between them.

Specifically, for the one-item bipolar scale, participants perceived that the accommodative response was more likely to be positioned in the stakeholder’s stance than the advocative response for both the focal organization ($t(278) = 9.44, p < .001$) and anchor organization ($t(418) = 11.91, p < .001$). Additionally, there was no difference in stance perception between both organizations for either the accommodative response ($t(338) = 1.17, p = .24$) or the advocative response ($t(358) = .83, p = .41$). Furthermore, the mean of advocative responses was below the midpoint while that of accommodative responses was above it.

Regarding the degree of accommodation, participants perceived that the accommodative response was more likely to be in stakeholders’ stance than the advocative response for both the focal organization ($t(278) = 10.05, p < .001$) and competitor ($t(418) = 10.42, p < .001$). Similarly to before, there were no differences in accommodating stance perception between organizations for either accommodative response($t(338) = 1.44, p = .15$) or advocative response($t(358) = .93, p = .35$).

The results of the advocation degree showed that participants perceived that an advocacy-based approach is more likely to align with organizational stances than an accommodation-based approach; this held true across both the focal organization ($t(278) = 8.88, p < .001$), and anchor organization ($t(418) = 12.06, p < .001$). There were no significant differences found between organizations regarding their perceptions of whether a given statement reflected an accommodating or advocating position; neither did they differ significantly when comparing their perceptions about which type of statement better aligned with each company’s respective stances (accommodating: $t(338) = 1.44, p = .15$; advocating: $t(358) = 1.40, p = .16$).

4.1.2. Main effect

Response strategy framing on reputation perception. A one-way ANOVA

Table 2
Result of crisis response stance manipulation checks in main test.

		Bi-polar stance perception		Degree of advocation		Degree of accommodation	
Organization	Stance	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
Anchor Organization	Advocative response	2.94	1.94	5.63	1.16	4.09	1.56
	Accommodative response	5.16	1.99	4.14	1.61	5.65	0.90
Organization	Advocative response	3.12	1.90	5.44	1.31	4.25	1.61
	Accommodative response	5.41	2.03	3.87	1.76	5.79	0.86

analysis revealed that the response strategy framing has a significant impact on reputation perception (with the pre-crisis reputation of the two brands controlled, $F_{anchor}(1416) = 1.07, p = .30, \eta^2 = .003$; $F_{focal}(1416) = 13.45, p < .001, \eta^2 = .031$). The study found that using an accommodative response ($M = 5.62, SD = 1.08$) resulted in better reputation perception from stakeholders compared to an advocative response ($M = 4.56, SD = 1.67$). This difference was statistically significant with $F(1, 416) = 56.35$ and $p < .001, R^2 = .16, \eta^2 = .119$.

Confidence on reputation perception. A one-way ANOVA analysis revealed that the stakeholder’s confidence has a significant impact on reputation perception (with the pre-crisis reputation of the two brands controlled, $F_{anchor}(1405) = 2.75, p = .98, \eta^2 = .007$; $F_{focal}(1416) = 4.10, p = .04, \eta^2 = .010$). The study found that when participant has more confidence in the organization resulted in better reputation perception from stakeholders. This difference was statistically significant with $F(12, 405) = 85.16$ and $p < .001, R^2 = .73, \eta^2 = .72$.

4.1.3. Moderation effect

Interaction effect on the dependent variable. A one-way ANOVA analysis (with the pre-crisis reputation of the two brands controlled, $F_{anchor}(1412) = .85, p = .36, \eta^2 = .002$; $F_{focal}(1412) = 13.89, p < .001, \eta^2 = .033$) indicates no interaction effect of response strategy selection and anchor stance on reputation perception ($F(2, 412) = 1.66, p = .19, R^2 = .17, \eta^2 = .008$).

Interaction effect on the mediating variable. A one-way ANOVA analysis (with the pre-crisis reputation of the two brands controlled, $F_{anchor}(1412) = .001, p = .99, \eta^2 < .001$; $F_{focal}(1412) = 10.74, p < .001, \eta^2 = .025$) indicates a significant interaction effect of response strategy selection and anchor stance on stakeholder’s confidence perception ($F(2, 412) = 3.64, p = .03, R^2 = .13, \eta^2 = .017$). More specifically, the interaction effect on confidence perception compared as follows.

Fig. 3 shows that in the scenario where there is no anchor stance, there was no significant difference in confidence perception between the accommodative stance response ($M = 5.53, SD = 1.12$) and advocative stance response ($M = 5.09, SD = 1.57$; $F(1, 412) = 3.84, p = .052, \eta^2 = .009$). However, when an accommodative stance anchor scenario was presented, the advocative stance response ($M = 4.80, SD = 1.61$) had lower confidence than the accommodative stance response ($M = 5.51, SD = .95$; $F(1412) = 14.24, p = .004, \eta^2 = .020$). This supports H1a, which suggests that if an organization’s response is lower than the level of accommodation of the anchor response, failing to keep up with it will result in a decrease in stakeholder confidence. Furthermore, when an advocative stance anchor scenario was presented, the accommodative stance response ($M = 5.89, SD = .78$) demonstrated higher confidence than the advocative stance response ($M = 4.66, SD = 1.49$; $F(1412) = 32.17, p < .001, \eta^2 = .072$). This finding supports H1b, which proposes that when an organization’s response exceeds the level of

Fig. 3. Vertical comparison of confidence perception between accommodative/advocative stance response in with/without anchor response presented scenarios. Note. AC means accommodative stance, while AD means advocative stance. When with no anchor stance, AC=AD ^{n.s.}. When with accommodative stance anchor, AC>AD ^{**}. When with advocative stance anchor, AC>AD ^{***}. Correlation significance level: ^{**}, p < .01; ^{***}, p < .001; n.s., no significance.

accommodation provided by the anchor response, stakeholder confidence in the organization will increase rather than following the anchor response. These results support H1, which suggests that stakeholders' confidence can be influenced by the anchoring bias in an organization's responses, depending on their level of accommodation.

4.1.4. Moderated mediation

We used the Model 7 of PROCESS (Hayes, 2022, with Bootstrap samples N = 5000, controlling for the pre-crisis reputation of the organizations, ($b_{anchor} = .06, SE = .04, CI [-.01 \text{ to } .13]$); ($b_{focal} = .06, SE = .03, CI [-.01 \text{ to } .12]$)).) to examine the anchoring effect of stance selection in crisis communication. The results (see Fig. 3 and Fig. 4) showed that stakeholder confidence significantly mediated the moderation effect of an organization's stance framing (accommodative=1 vs. advocative=0) and anchor stance (accommodative vs. advocative vs. not present) during a spillover crisis on organizational reputation ($b = .36, SE = .13, CI [.10 \text{ to } .61], R^2 = .72$).

Specifically, we found no difference between accommodative and advocative stance responses on organizational reputation through the mediation of stakeholder's confidence when there was no anchor response ($b = .31, SE = .18, CI [-.04 \text{ to } .68]$). However, when an accommodative anchor stance was presented following an accommodative response instead of an advocative one resulted in a better reputation evaluation due to stakeholders' increased confidence in their

competence ($b = .67, SE = .12, CI [.44 \text{ to } .91]$). The gap would be amplified when an advocative stance anchor was presented; using an accommodative response would win more confidence from stakeholders than simply following an advocative stance response resulting in increased perception of reputation ($b = 1.03, SE = .17, CI [.71 \text{ to } 1.36]$).

Our findings confirm H2 which suggests that stakeholder confidence acts as a predictor for publics' responses such as organizational reputation and indicates that higher levels of stakeholder confidence lead them towards perceiving organizations' reputations positively.

5. Discussion

5.1. Key findings

Firstly, this study reveals that the selection of organizational crisis response strategies is influenced by an anchoring effect, where the level of accommodation in a competitor's crisis response serves as an anchor point. In particular, when there is no anchor response available, it does not matter to the organization whether they provide an accommodative or advocative response because there is no difference in stakeholders' reaction and confidence towards the organization. However, when an anchor response is present, using either an accommodative or advocative approach to respond to a spillover crisis becomes significant.

Secondly, the strength of the anchoring bias between an accommodative and advocative response would increase based on the level of accommodation in the anchor response. If an organization provides an advocative response, stakeholders' confidence towards that organization decreases compared to if they were to follow a competitor's accommodative response. Conversely, using an accommodative response leads to higher stakeholder confidence compared to following a competitor's advocative response. Furthermore, this bias is more pronounced when an advocative response serves as the anchor rather than an accommodative one.

Thirdly, our study reveals that the public's confidence in an organization's crisis management abilities can predict its reputation during spillover crises. Specifically, if an organization responds with advocacy, it may experience a decrease in reputation compared to adopting a competitor's accommodative response. This is because stakeholders lose confidence in the organization. Conversely, using an accommodative response can lead to higher organizational reputation than following a competitor's advocative response as it enhances stakeholder confidence.

Fig. 4. The effect of response stance framing and anchor stance on organizational reputation through the mediation of stakeholder's confidence.

5.2. Theoretical contribution

This study contributes to the contingency theory of accommodation by highlighting the importance of considering situational factors such as competitor responses. Our findings indicate that anchor bias is present not only in crisis preparedness (Paulus, 2022), but also in how the public perceives an organization's response to a crisis when other competitors are involved. In such spillover crises, stakeholders use a competitor's level of accommodation in their crisis response as a benchmark for evaluating other companies' responses to the same situation. Our study adds to Barnett and Hoffman's (2008) three strategic themes for responding to spillover crises by emphasizing the need to consider competitors' accommodation levels in their responses before taking action. Our findings suggest that it is beneficial to keep up with the Jones's who are accommodating in their responses, while fencing out with the Jones's would provide a competitive advantage for the organization when competitors' responses are not accommodative enough. However, there appears to be no difference in using an accommodative or advocative response when an anchor response is unavailable. This could be due to the absence of reference points for adjusting stakeholders' range of plausible accommodation levels without an anchor response. Consequently, they may lack criteria to determine whether a response is appropriate or not (Furnham & Boo, 2011).

Furthermore, this study is the first to apply Pang et al.'s (2020) continuum of public response of confidence in an empirical research setting. The SCCT system for prescribing responses during a crisis was developed with crisis responsibility as the primary factor (Coombs, 2021; Coombs & Holladay, 2002). However recently, many new measures based on image repair theory have challenged the SCCT conception of crisis. For instance, Page (2022) has proposed a revised model of reputation repair called REMREP that replaces crisis responsibility in the SCCT model with offensiveness and virtuousness. Page's (2019, 2022) findings implies that the crisis responses did not alter people's perceptions of the crisis situation itself. Instead, they influenced how people viewed the organization involved in the crisis, particularly its moral character like virtuousness. Additionally, this study presents evidence that the continuum of public response confidence proposed by Pang et al. (2020) could be another potential valuable tool for understanding how crises can impact reputation. Moreover, this study offers insight into the complex spiral interplay between an organization's accommodation and public confidence over time.

In addition, our research findings indicate that corrective action response strategy through addressing vulnerabilities can enhance an organization's legitimacy and competitive advantage (Veil et al., 2016). This also echoes Veil et al.'s (2020) suggestion to convince the public of a substantial response to an unsubstantiated claim. This study supports Veil et al. (2016) that when an organization faces reputational and industry legitimacy threats due to a spillover crisis, simply denying responsibility for causing the crisis is not sufficient. Laufer and Wang (2018) suggested that organizations may face guilt by association due to factors beyond industry similarity, resulting in various vulnerabilities. However, it is unclear whether taking corrective action in such cases caused by other risk factors can positively impact the organization's reputation (Veil et al., 2012). Therefore, before engaging with the public during spillover crises, it is important to carefully test the thumb rule of "the more accommodation, the better".

5.3. Managerial application

Use Anchors to Organization's Advantage. The anchoring bias has an impact on our everyday decisions, such as purchasing and important work-related choices. Our research indicates that stakeholders' views of how an organization responds to a crisis can be also influenced by the level of accommodation in competitors' responses. Therefore, PR practitioners can use competitor responses as a reference point when making strategic response decisions going forward during spillover crises. Our

research indicates that organizations can gain an advantage by adopting a "fencing out with the Jones's" strategy when competitors' responses are insufficiently accommodating. This approach, which involves anchoring off the Jones's, can enhance both competitiveness and legitimacy for the organization (Veil et al., 2016).

Be the First and the Most Accommodation to Escape Being Anchored. As an organization can take advantage of competitor's response as anchor to enhance its competitive advantages. However, caution must be exercised to avoid being anchored by competitors during crises. In certain situations, an organization may need to be the first in its industry to respond to a crisis and reduce the severity of the threat and urgency of the situation (Pang et al., 2010). Our research suggests that issuing a response that adequately accommodates stakeholders is often the safest way for organizations to escape being anchored in such cases. However, in case being anchored, it is better to keep up with the Jones's if you have no more to accommodate stakeholders. Strategic communication should not always result in equal benefits for both parties, nor should it lead to a win-lose situation. Rather, it requires continuous dialogue and negotiation (Pang et al., 2020). Practitioners must avoid getting into an endless competition where both parties are mutually anchored.

5.4. Limitations and future study

First, it is important to note the impact of cultural differences in crisis communication, as our findings are based on the Chinese context. Crisis communication theories are predominantly built on Western case studies (Diers-Lawson, 2017), and it remains a challenge to generalize Western frameworks to the Eastern context (Rasmussen & Ihlen, 2017). For instance, Lee (2005) discovered that Hong Kong stakeholders tend to be less sympathetic than Westerners toward organizations' responses due to the influence of the "emotion is to be restrained" Chinese philosophy. In Asian culture, a verbal apology is often perceived as a routine and ritualistic behavior, leading stakeholders in Hong Kong to prefer practical offers like compensation over verbal apologies compared to their Western counterparts (Lee, 2004). Furthermore, cultural differences were found to impact the anchoring effect of prior ratings on subsequent customers' online behaviors, highlighting the fundamental role of culture in shaping individuals' personal characteristics (Wang et al., 2022). It is crucial to replicate experiments before generalizing the findings of the current study to Western cultural contexts.

We examined the anchoring effect of response message selection, specifically in short-term spillover crisis scenarios. However, it remains unclear whether this effect occurs in other types of crises and how it operates in the long term (see Jong & van der Linde, 2022). A spillover crisis is a unique type of crisis that arises when "events in an external organization create concern, uncertainty, or perceptions of harm for another organization" (Veil et al., 2016, p.317). In most cases, organizations are not responsible for creating the crisis event in spillover crises. Nevertheless, investigating the mechanism behind the anchoring effect when organizations bear responsibility would strengthen our findings. In such cases, responses that have been widely acknowledged by stakeholders during previous industry crises may serve as self-generated anchors (Epley & Gilovich, 2001). Furthermore, as the effect of crisis communication may differ in the short term and long term (Coombs & Tachkova, 2019), responses toward similar crises from competitors in industry crisis history may still impact stakeholders' perception of the ongoing crisis. For instance, every time there is a battery-heating crisis, Samsung's scandal in 2016 always makes headlines and reminds stakeholders of how they responded in that crisis. Therefore, investigating the mechanism behind the anchoring effect in preventable crises and how long an anchoring effect will last should be our next research agenda.

Thirdly, in this study, we initially used the level of accommodation as an anchor point to investigate the anchoring effect in response message framing. However, it is important to note that an anchor can be any

parameter, such as the intensity of emotions or empathy expressed by organizations. Lazarus, (1991) discrete emotion theory categorizes emotions into various types on a continuum from lower-order automatic responses to higher-order complex ones. Previous research has compared expressing specific emotions versus factual or mixed-valence expressions (Schoofs & Claey, 2021; Xiao et al., 2018). Nevertheless, it remains unclear whether and how the emotional intensity continuum can serve as an anchor in crisis response. For instance, as noted by Xiao et al. (2018), expressing emotions may implicitly disclose the cause of the crisis, and this effect could vary when a lower-order emotion is expressed after a higher-order emotion by competitors.

Fourthly, the measurement of confidence in the current study is derived from Hon and Grunig's (1999) organizational trust scale for competence. This choice is informed by Pang et al.'s (2020) confidence continuum, which emphasizes stakeholders' confidence in an organization's ability to handle a crisis. Moreover, in the context of organizational reputation during cyberattack crises, it is predominantly about customers' confidence in the organization's responsible management of their personal data (Syed, 2019). Confidence in a crisis is a complex matter that shares similarities with and differences from trust. Future research should aim for a more direct measure of stakeholders' confidence in a crisis to draw more definite conclusions about the potential spiral relationship between an organization's stance (accommodation-advocacy) and the public's stance (confidence-doubt), and how this relationship impacts stakeholders' evaluation processes in organizational crises.

Fifthly, In the realm of crisis communication, particularly in the face of cyber-attacks, a notable phenomenon is the tendency of organizations to opt for silence. Therefore, it is important to consider that an organization facing a spillover crisis might decide to remain silent. According to Roehm and Tybout (2006), companies with a low risk of crisis contagion may choose not to respond. This strategic decision aims to avoid drawing unnecessary attention, as issuing a denial could inadvertently raise concerns and lead people to question whether the organization has something to hide. It would be relevant to explore whether maintaining silence during a spillover crisis becomes more effective when a competitor has already issued a crisis response, and conversely whether the competitor's decision to remain silent could serve as an anchor for subsequent crisis responses.

Lastly, in our study, we investigate the anchoring effect in the context of a spillover crisis among organizations within the cybersecurity domain. Cybersecurity crises often exhibit pronounced spillover effects due to the interconnected nature of digital technologies and the shared vulnerabilities across various platforms and systems. However, the experiment might yield different results based on the chosen industry. As noted by Laufer and Wang (2018), a spillover effect can also have negative consequences for organizations that share the same country of origin, organizational type, and positioning strategy. Therefore, it would be valuable to explore how this anchoring effect would be replicated in other industries.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest. This research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest. The authors have adhered to ethical standards in the preparation of this manuscript, ensuring the integrity of the research process. No funding was received from agencies or organizations that could influence the content of this research. The findings and interpretations presented in this study are solely the responsibility of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views of their affiliated institutions.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Appendix A. Script of the news report¹

Breaking News: Over 10,000 user information on 115 Cloud Storage may have been leaked

Is cloud storage really safe? Chinese personal cloud storage company, 115 Cloud Storage, has just confirmed being attacked by foreign hackers and over 10,000 users' data may have been compromised. According to industry insiders, the file-sharing mechanism of 115 Cloud Storage may have vulnerabilities that led to the attack by hackers. The incident is still under investigation.

It is understood that among cloud storage products in China, 115 Cloud Storage ranks third in terms of user volume with Baidu Netdisk and Tencent Micro-Cloud ranking first and second respectively. It is currently unknown whether other similar products have suffered from similar attacks. Discussions about the security of cloud storage are also trending today.

Appendix B. Anchor response from Tencent

Advocating response

The online rumor about "Tencent Micro-Cloud being hacked" is false information. Please do not believe or spread rumors. There are no related vulnerabilities in the file sharing mechanism of Tencent Micro-Cloud cloud storage product, and user information data has not been attacked or leaked!

In terms of storage security, there have been no data losses caused by illegal attacks in the ten years since its establishment. Tencent Micro-Cloud has always had leading security performance nationwide. Please continue to trust Tencent Micro-Cloud!

Accommodating response

The online rumor about "Tencent Micro-Cloud being hacked" is false information. Please do not believe or spread rumors.

The recent 115 cloud storage incident has also sounded the alarm for Tencent Micro-Cloud. We will take it as a warning and continue to improve the security performance of our cloud storage, safeguarding the information security of our users and ensuring that no similar incidents affect any Tencent Micro-Cloud user's rights and interests. Thank you for your trust and support in Micro-Cloud!

Appendix C. Crisis response from Baidu

Advocating response

Thank you for your concern. Baidu Netdisk was not involved in this incident. None of the user information data on Baidu Netdisk has been attacked or leaked, and our file sharing mechanism does not have any vulnerabilities!

With a comprehensive security protection system, Baidu Netdisk has won the Excellent Security Design Award for Cloud Computing Products in the cloud storage industry for ten consecutive years. We will continue to maintain industry-leading security performance advantages and hope that everyone will continue to support Baidu Netdisk!

Accommodating response

Thank you for your concern. Baidu Netdisk was not involved in this incident. However, user information security is of great importance and Baidu Netdisk will take it seriously.

¹ Note that the original language for the stimuli is Chinese. The stimuli shown in the appendix is an approximate translation of the original version.

We will learn from the lessons of 115 Cloud, uphold the principle of putting users' rights first, continuously upgrade the security performance of our network disk, ensure the safety of users' information, and prevent similar incidents from happening to any Baidu Netdisk user. Please continue to support Baidu Netdisk!

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